

A STUDY ON WOMEN INVESTORS PREFERENCE TOWARDS INVESTMENT AVENUES

Dr. S. Tamilselvi

Principal & Associate Professor in Commerce, Maharani Arts and Science
College, Dharapuram, Tirupur, Tamilnadu

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Abstract:

In today's world women are the best home maker and financier of every family. Women today have more earning potential and more influence over the financial decisions than ever before. In this paper, an attempt has been made to find out the women investors preference towards investment avenues. A sample of 100 respondent's was conveniently selected from Coimbatore District. The selected samples are analyzed using simple percentage and ranking method. It is found that most of the women investors have high level of preference towards investment avenues. The study also concludes that safety was the first preference factor of the investors to create investment.

Key Words: Investment, Women, Investor, Finance, Attitude, Preference, Avenues & Factor Etc

Introduction:

In olden days, women were considered for the handling the kitchen and children. If women were educated then there was a misunderstanding that she would extinct the system of the Hindu family. The other reason is ego which is mostly carried by men if women are highly educated than men then the ego of men was hurt. In some areas because of poverty parents don't allow their kids for education. In India now a days it is seen that women are working together with men in every field. It is important for the developing the India from the developing India to developed India women are the strength of the nation. In each and every field it can be seen that the woman are working in high post .Now, women are not only meant for the caring the house, she crosses her limit and achieves her goals. Throughout their lives as a women, they will be faced with different challenges than their male counter parts. If women are going to take control of their financial future, it is important that they recognize those differences and empower themselves. A reasonable salary can be earned by women, this would help their family to pay rental obligation, medical expenses and raising cost of education. Still more women are interested in saving their earnings and converting it into investment for future benefits like children's education, children's marriage and purchasing or constructing of houses.

Review of Literature:

Bhardwaj Rajesh, Raheja Rekh & Priyanka (2011) analyzed the Income and Savings Pattern of Government and Private Senior Secondary School Women investors. The research founded that the main source of income of Government women investors is salary and tuition fee for private women investors. The researcher revealed that government & private women investors both used Bank Deposits and Life Insurance for investing their savings. Government school women investors received more perks in comparison to private women investors. The important objective of savings of women investors is an emergency , security while for private women investors is children education and purchase of consumer durable.

Dr. S. Mathivannan & Dr. M. Selvakumar (2011) examined the saving and investment pattern of school teaches in Sivakasi Taluk. The research founded that the teaching community has stated realizing the importance of money and money's worth. The research concludes that investors are initiated to prepare a budget for the proposed expenses and compare it with the actual expenses met by them. From this budget the school teachers they are not influence by other tempting and fashionable expenses.

Hoang Thanh Hue Ton (2014), aimed to find out whether there is the discrepancy among classified groups of investors or not (the discrepancy in the risk taking investment decisions between male and female, in same age group, education, investment experience, income and marital status) , and they illustrated that male have more willingness to take risks in making investment decision than female; the elderly or retirement investors make the options of not taking risk; the investors with five-year-or-more investment experience often take higher risks than the others; have the same ability to take risk; the single investors show a tendency to take higher risks than married investors.

Statement of the Problem:

In today's world, people are very happy in increasing their wealth. So they are in search of best investment avenues to invest their hardly earned money in a proper place. In the modern environment we have to spend more amounts on education, medical expenses and infrastructures. So everyone is running to increase

their earnings. Without proper plan of spending we may have to go for borrowing loans. Women are considered to be wise and knowledgeable persons, so they make good efforts in making their investments for their future carrier. An attempt has been made in this study that how do the women now about investment avenues and what are the investment avenues and what are the investment pattern selected by them.

Objective of the Study:

- ✓ To determine the investment pattern among women investors.
- ✓ To study the women investors preference towards investment avenues.

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ The study is applicable only to the women investors.
- ✓ The results of the study are based upon the views expressed by the women investors.
- ✓ The statistical method used to analyze the data has their own limitation.
- ✓ All the limitations of primary data are applicable to this study.

Methodology: The type of data collected and the method of sampling are explained under this head.

Data Collection:

A sample of 100 respondent’s was conveniently selected from Coimbatore District. The data required for the study have been collected through well structured questionnaire. Hence the study is based on primary data. The questionnaire consists of questions relating to personal details, investment details etc., the secondary data required for the study have been collected from various publications, reports and websites.

Statistical Tools: Data collected from the women investors have been analyzed with the help of the following statistical tools. The statistical tools are:

- ✓ Simple Percentage
- ✓ Ranking Method

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Personal Profile

Factors	No. of Women Investors	Percentage
Age		
Less than 25 years	26	26
26-35 years	35	35
36-45 years	30	30
Above 45 years	19	19
Educational Qualification		
Upto HSC	24	24
Diploma	13	13
UG	45	45
PG	18	18
Occupation		
Employee	42	42
Profession	20	20
Business	38	38
Marital status		
Married	63	63
Unmarried	37	37
Type of Family		
Nuclear	70	70
Joint	30	30
Number of Members in family		
Upto 2 members	38	38
3 to 5 members	46	46
More than 5 members	16	16

Table 1 describes the demographic profile of the women investors. Out of 100 women investors who were taken for the study: it has been identified that (35%) of the women age group is between 26 to 35 years, most (45%) of the women investors are graduates, (42%) of the women investors are employees, (63%) of them are married, (70%) of the women investors belong to nuclear family and (46%) of them have 3 to 5 members in their family.

Table 2: Economic Profile

Factors	No. of Women Investors	Percentage
Number of earning Members in family		
Two	57	57
Three	21	21

Above 3	22	22
Family Income per month		
Upto Rs.15,000	45	45
Rs.15,000 to Rs.30,000	30	30
Rs. 30,000 to Rs. 45,000	19	19
Above Rs.45,000	6	6
Investing Years		
Less than 5 Years	22	22
6-10 Years	53	53
Above 10 Years	25	25
Proportion for Investment		
Upto 15%	45	45
16%- 30%	35	35
31%- 45%	13	13
Above 45%	7	7

Table n2 describes the economic profile of the women investors. Out of 100 women investors who were taken for the study: it has been identified that (57%) of the women investors have above 3 members in the family, monthly income of (45%) women investors is up to Rs.15,000, (53%) of the women investors are investing for a period of 6-10 years and (45%) of the women investors invest up to 15% of their income.

Table 3: Investment Details

Factors	No. of Women Investors	Percentage
Source		
Print media	30	30
Friends/Relatives	46	46
Neighbourhood	24	24
Investment Avenues		
Chit funds	8	8
Post Office savings	12	12
Bank Deposit	21	21
Gold	40	40
Real estate	14	14
Debenture & bonds	5	5

Table 3 describes the investment details of the women investors. Out of 100 women investors who were taken for the study: it has been identified that most (26%) of the women investors came to know about the investment avenue through Friends/Relatives and (40%) of the women investors prefer to invest in gold.

Table 4: Level of preference towards investment media

Factors	No. of Women Investors	Percentage
Low	16	16
Medium	29	29
High	55	55

From the above table, it shows that out of 100 women investors (55%) of the women investors level of preference is high towards investment media, (29%) of the women investors level of preference is medium and (16%) of the women investors level of preference is low towards investment media.

Table 5: Preference Factors towards Investment

Factors	Total Score	Rank
Safety	768	1
Liquidity	715	2
Profitability	669	4
Capital Appreciation	386	7
Speculation	558	5
Tax Benefits	674	3
Stability	497	6

It is found from the above table, that safety was the first factor preference of the women investors to create investment, Liquidity was ranked as the second factor to choose investment media, Tax benefits was ranked as third factor; Profitability was ranked as fourth factor; Speculation was the fifth factor; Stability was the sixth factor and Capital appreciation was the seventh factor.

Conclusions:

This report is a reflection of the investment behavior of women investors. Selection of a perfect investment avenue is a difficult task to any investor. An effort is made to identify the preferences of a sample of women investors selected from large population. This report concentrated in identifying the needs of present and future preference towards various investment avenues are identified based on their income. This study confirms the earlier findings with regard to the relationship between Age and risk tolerance level of women investors. Women are less likely to take investment risks for whatever reason many women are less willing than men to take risks. It can be concluded from the study that a woman always makes an investment as a precaution to the future such as safety, regular income and tax benefits. The study also concludes that most women investors are interested to invest in gold.

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